

GLOBALIZATION AND THE SPREAD OF ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION

English language is a language before Globalization; English is the language after Globalization. Globalization and English language are said to work as pull factors for one another. English language plays a major role in the progress of Globalization. Globalization of trade and commerce, increasing diversities of work force with different setup values have increased the importance of English language usage.

Man has been using language as a medium of communication for the ages, today due to Globalization English language has become the most prized possession of communication. In this Global village, English language acts as a repository of wisdom and wit. English language is a propeller for advancement of career and a machine to mint money. And it is a telescope to view the vision of future. In this Global world, communication in English is now recognized as an inseparable part rather the life blood of every activity which occurs in our day to day life. Now a day's every organization functions through a communication process, wherein mutually independent persons create and exchange messages to articulate and achieve commonly held objectives and goals.

English language can be rightly regarded as the key to the store house of production and productivity. We can make use of this language to promote our world view and spiritual heritage and promote cultural and traditional aspects across the

globe. Globalization has brought English language into limelight. The scenario of the usage of the language has changed drastically. The Queen's language has become a common man's curriculum. The language has become a silver bowl to earn one's bread and butter.

In this Global world English is the language of the latest business management. English language is not only a means for international commerce, it has become increasingly essential for inter-state commerce and communication. It is the official language of air transfers and shipping, the leading language of science and technology, computers and commerce and a major medium of education. In an era of increased communication through the telephones, fax machine, television and modem, the world is becoming more and more globally oriental. Business, families, friends and many other groups with common interests are able to form small tele or cyber communications that transcend geographical boundaries.

Key words: *globalization, international language, economics, cultural, political, science, technology, entrepreneurs.*

INTRODUCTION:

The word Globalization is the buzzing word to all economists, a magical word to entrepreneurs and a material word to the governments and all other business people. Globalization is the trump card for the rapid development across the globe in terms of language, culture, tradition, customs, lifestyle, economy and science and technology.

If we go back to the origin and existence of this term Globalization, the term has been there in the annals of history and it got its significance just a decade ago. It started on the point of business then spread like a wild fire to all aspects of human's survival. Technological advances in production, transportation, and tele-communication and more advancement with internet the firms got access to customer's supplies and collaborators around the world. Globalization originated with trade and marketing and crossed the national boundaries to connect people. Globalization has brought

everything together but the English language made Globalization more possible and effective one.

Due to globalization, English language emerged as a global force. As statistics say English language is the most widely spoken tongue in the world today. It is English language, however, a bigger impact on the world as a whole and has become the global de-facto standard used in business, cultural, political and linguistic exchange.

One of the main reasons why English is the international language in the world today is the fact that Britain was the global superpower in the nineteenth century and America is the global superpower in the twentieth and twenty-first. For example, these two English-speaking countries were the most important countries in terms of the military and trade. By conquering and colonizing sum of the world, their customs, culture and way of life became common in those parts of the world. This is why so many ex-British colonies now have English as the national language, with many of their people speaking English as a first language.

Another reason for the spread of English is economics. By being the global political and military superpower, these two countries also became the leading trading nations and many countries and territories needed to learn English in order to trade with them. The USA is currently a major trading partner with almost every other country on the planet due to the size of the consumer economy. This explains why in many countries, English is a compulsory subject in all levels at school.

Therefore, the factors of political history and finance are the most important reasons why English is the current global language.

Nowdays English is no longer a very unusual thing, but English has become the norm especially in the era of globalization. Able to speak well and fluently English no longer be an added value, but it has become demands or needs for every people in today's era of globalization. This is because English language influence in almost all aspects in life.

English not only as an academic requirement for mastery is limited in aspects of language knowledge, but also as a language of science and technology. It means that

English is used to communicate and interact in science and technology. Seemingly that most of the utilizing terms of English, and even a variety of documents and technical guidelines for the use and improvement of a device that speaks English. According to the research that have been noted by Maurais and Morris (2003), the field of science and technology also rely on the English language. From one billion documents on the website in 1990s, amounting to 86,5 % used in English.

English also used to cooperate in the world of business with entrepreneurs from various countries. Job opportunities for someone who mastered the English language is wide open to welcome work in companies or private organizations or government agencies, also be able to get a good position in that company or institution. It is complicated for someone to gain the considerable job without skill of English. In an increasingly globalized business world, a number of local companies including the Indonesian company has entered into the world trade and use English as the main communication tool, and at the height of international companies that enters to the local trade due to the use of English language of business which became increasingly perceived as a necessity.

English will become an international lingua franca for at least the next fifty years and no single language will occupy the monopolistic position in the twenty first century (Graddol, 1997). As an international lingua franca, English not only called as a medium of global communication, but also plays in more important role in education, business, diplomacy, technology, commerce, industry, banking, computing, medicine, aviation, engineering, cultures, social instructions, even in all aspects of life.

Looking at the fact, the capability of English will become the contributing factor of success in academic and job. Therefore, in this era of globalization it is important to learn or speak English or other foreign languages. Most people believe that the era of globalization is very important to master at least English or other foreign languages. Another claim that if without mastery of English language is good, a country will not advance.

“English rules” is an old phrase, “English language rules” is the new phrase emerged out of Globalization. Knowledge of English is very essential because countries are becoming globally integrated and coupled with each other in all aspects in terms of culture, economy, trade and commerce. This integration can happen only when language spoken is the same.

As per the international publication “Economist”, said India has multi languages out of these English is the only language understood all over India. Language remains potentially a communicating medium capable of expressing ideas and concepts as well as moods, feelings, thoughts and ideas. English language has revolutionized science and technology. It has become the main tool in computer languages and components. The purpose of the language and its influence leading to common objective. Computers are the most important technical tool that has revolutionised all walks of life and communication is no exception to the phenomenon. The English language has taken u-turn after globalization. The musing language has become an item of economic value. Due to Globalization the companies are using English language as a medium to sell their products across the globe. There are constant advertisements in print and electronic media English language sweeps all the advertisements. Globalization leaves no stone unturned, as current Globalization seems to demand comprehensive transformation of a society, its impact on language and culture be detected in every facet of life.

The parliament has also recognized English as an official language in addition to Hindi. Realising the importance of English language then railway minister Laloo Prasad yadav demanded teaching of English language in schools. The greater demand for admission in English medium schools throughout the country is a testimony to the attraction of English to the people of India.

We can make use of English language to promote our world view and spiritual heritage throughout the globe. Some spiritual gurus have been using this language to establish cultural identity. Swami Vivekananda established our identity in overseas and manifested our culture with this language.

The main reasons for language Globalization are a] rule of British colonies b] exchange of socio-economic, political and technological advancements c] new trends in education system d] changing trends in market and world economy e] improved means of communication.

Conclusion: There is no doubt that Globalization has changed the face of English language. In fact, Globalization has changed the life style of human beings altogether, the English language has given a new life to the modern man.

A sea change has taken place in the selection process especially at corporate sector that is because of Globalization. Communication in English is the major requirement in the day-to-day selection process.

Today English is news; the language continues to make news daily in many parts of the world. If English language is not your mother tongue you may still have mixed feelings about it. You may be strongly motivated to learn the English language because you know it will put you in touch with more people than any other language. It gives you scope to work anywhere across the globe. More over it will give you economic, political and cultural status in the society.

As I started “English” is a language before Globalization and “English” is the language after globalization and I end with the same phrase.

Finally, English and Globalization are inseparable, living one on another in the present day world like body and soul of a human being.

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